

Simple and Affordable ICT Tools to Develop Learning Materials

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Abstract

Classroom teaching can no longer depend on textbooks and whiteboard because the present condition in classrooms shows that teachers should find ways to make learning more enticing and engaging. Books, pictures, and videos are no longer enough for students and some teachers realize that textbooks assigned by curriculum are just insufficient to cater both teachers' and students' demands. As Information Communication Technology (ICT) gradually becomes part of human life, there are calls for teachers to use ICT in developing learning materials which can elevate students' learning experience, beyond textbooks and whiteboard. That said, ICT opens rooms for teachers to innovate with existing learning materials and provide students with tailor-made lessons which, teachers deem, are in-tune to students' needs and capabilities. For example, with ICT, teachers can create podcasts/videocasts which can be uploaded into internet, make online quizzes, or starting a digital classroom.

The success of Khan Academy, Corsera, and Edmodo prove that ICT has solid performance to support learning outside classroom. Although, ICT is full of potentials to help teachers developing learning materials, there are negative opinions about this approach. First, ICT demands teachers to take a serious training to achieve mastery. Then, using ICT made teachers spend money on commercial softwares/applications. In addition, ICT comes in various types that make teachers confused about which one they should use in classroom. Finally, ICT might not work reliably for both teachers and students alike. On the bright side, there are a few ICT tools that work wonderfully simple, available in multiple platforms, and are helpful for teachers to churn innovative learning materials by using those ICT tools, regardless of technology platforms that teachers and students use. The best thing about these tools is that they are affordable.

Keywords: ICT, applications, Windows, Macintosh, Android, iOS, freeware.

The boom of internet 2.0 in mid 2000's has ushered an era of interaction and connectivity that sprawls beyond what used to be considered almost impossible. With its strong ground in inter-connection and content distribution (O'Reilly, 2005), Web 2.0, marked by the popularity of user-generated-content websites—Friendster, Blogger, Wikipedia, FB, Twitter—has now offered bigger opportunities for educators to harness internet potential to extend their teaching without having to learn sophisticated programming skill. Therefore, teachers can create websites/blogs and fill them with educational content. On the other side, students can then take the content and use it to support their learning outside classroom. Thus, the traditional classroom interaction is enriched and transformed into blended learning, flipping classroom, and massive open online course (MOOC). This new reality of education is easily found in the success of Moodle, teaching/learning blog, YouTube classes, Coursera, and many more. Although each of those teaching learning medium has its own special feature, every one of them has one thing in common: using audio/video as media of extended teaching (Kaufman and Mohan, 2009).

Though teaching using video/audio is not a new thing (distant learning method has pioneered this), it has become more widespread these days due to the growing success of video-sharing websites, such as, YouTube, Vimeo, and Dailymotion, and iTunes Store. Those places house hundreds of educational channels which most of them are available for free and accessible for anyone. Video and audio are regarded as a perfect companion to textbook because they convert words and sentences into a realistic learning (Harmer, 2011) and they add details that are missing in textbooks. For instance, a teacher can create a video to demonstrate a theory in a textbook with additional information that is taken from other sources (Hoffenberg and Handler, 2001). As to audio teaching, a teacher may create a recorded lecture that explains a chapter in a textbook (Harmer, 2011). Therefore, by watching the videocast or listening to audio podcast several times, students will get better comprehension than just learning from textbooks. This means students can learn a subject according to their own pace, depending on their academic ability (Dawson, 2011). In addition to that, students can learn anywhere and anytime using the already powerful mobile gadgets or they can use desktop computer (Jee, 2011). Furthermore, audio/videocast is potential to facilitate students with special needs--dyslectic or autistic) (Burn and Reed, 1999). The benefits of this audio/video teaching approach are to allow teachers to create a rich learning material that is free from the constraints of schedule, to allow repetitive learning, to retain the same intimacy of teacher-students interaction, and to stimulate students' multiple intelligences.

One notable success story of using videocast for education is Khan Academy (Thompson, 2011). Other successful educational channel on internet is MOOC, such as, Coursera and Udemy, and podcasts library on iTunes Store. Those successes show how strong the internet is to boost teaching and learning condition beyond the scope of classroom wall and schedule.

Using Video in Classroom

Videos have been used to supplement students learning in classroom before internet age. Besides using ready made videos which are available in music/video stores, teachers occasionally have the need to use videos which are available for free on internet. The problem is that only few videos on internet can be downloaded for free and most of the videos are not downloadable. With a simple software, teachers can download videos from websites, such as, YouTube or Daily Motion, without having to spend money.

JDownloader (JD) is a download manager, similar to IDM, that can download almost anything from a website and it is free. This program is free because it is built on Java, so it does not require users to purchase it. To use this program, users only need to copy a web link (or download link) and paste it into its JD's Linkgrabber tab. When it is done, JDownloader will read the link and process it. Later, user only need to click Download button and wait until it finishes downloading the file. JD can download almost any kind of files from internet. If it is used to download a video from YouTube, it is going to read the web address and provide various types of downloadable video format (FLV, MOV, MP4, etc) in multiple resolutions (240p-720p, etc). The best thing about JD is its ability to pause a download process and resume it anytime. Even if the process is halted because

of power shutdown, users can resume the download process whenever the computer is on. This makes JD feels like a torrent-download software.

In case JDownloader feels a bit impractical and too sophisticated, there is another simple way to download video; Downloadhelper (DwH). DwH is a small plug-in that can download video, usually, from video-hosting websites-YouTube and Vimeo. This plug-in can be downloaded directly from Firefox browser. Users just open Firefox, click Tools on toolbar, click Add-ons, and type “downloadhelper” in search box. Then, user only need to follow simple instruction and the plug-in will be installed right inside Firefox. So, whenever Firefox is open, “downloadhelper” will be ready to work. If the user visit a video address on YouTube, users will see rotating red-yellow-blue balls on the right corner of Firefox browser. That means Downloadhelper is able to read the video file in the web address and ready to download it. Still, users have to choose which type of video that they want to download (MP4, FLV, High Quality, Medium Resolution, etc). Once a choice is selected. users just sit and wait until the file is downloaded.

It is recommended that teachers download video in MP4 since it is the most common format for video and playable by most media players. Avoid downloading 3gp format because of its low screen resolution and skip flash-based video (FLV) due to its high energy consumption.

Making Podcasts and Videocasts

Often times, teachers are not satisfied with ready-made video and they want to make a tailor-made video which is specifically designed to meet classroom’s need and students ability. Furthermore, the podcasts/videocasts will enable students to stay up-to-date with the progress of classroom learning and both teachers and students reap benefits. Students can listen to podcasts or watch videocasts in case they have not understood the lesson in class textbook or they miss their class. On the other hand, teachers can give enriching lesson, using materials outside textbooks.

Podcasts are basically an audio record of teachers talk. The content is usually about an explanation of a subject that a teacher teaches. Making podcasts is quite simple because a teacher can choose to record his/her voice during actual classroom session or he/she create a special session to record his/her teaching. If the teacher choose the first technique, the teacher should prepare a voice recorder (smartphone or digital voice recorder) and put it in his shirt’s pocket. Then, he can record his voice in real-time while he is teaching. In terms of audio quality, voice recorder can produce acceptable audio quality but smartphone cannot produce similar result. To overcome that weak spot, a smartphone needs external microphone, such as, a plug-in mic or a lavalier mic. With lavalier mic, the teacher only need to attach it to the teacher’s shirt, connect it to his smartphone, and do his teaching as usual. On the other side, plug-in mic is simpler to use because the teacher just plug the mic into the headphone port, put the phone in pocket shirt (for better reception), and does his business as usual. As to software, usually every smartphone comes with its own pre-installed app that can record voice. If the app is not satisfying, it is possible to look for free app for voice recording in Google Store or iTunes Store. iRig Recorder or EZ Voice (free apps for iOS and Android) from IK Multimedia is very recommended for this job.

If a teacher plans to make a podcast with a computer, he/she can use Audacity (freeware) and an external microphone. External microphone for computer is easy to get because teachers can use any available mic on the market or use a headphone with ext. mic. As to Audacity, ones can download it for free from internet (Audacity.sourceforge.net) and install it in ones' computer (Windows or Mac). However, installing Audacity can be tricky because it comes in 3 separate packages and they all have to be installed because they are inter-related. To be safe, follow the procedure described in Sourceforge's website. Once installed, Audacity can do any audio-related project, e.g., record voice, convert audio file, modify a record, etc. The graphic user interface (GUI) of Audacity is quite easy to understand. Just click the red (record) button and the teacher can start recording his voice. When he is finished, he can click the red square button to stop recording. After that, teacher may save the recording file and convert the file into media friendly format (mp3 or aac)

While podcasts are easy to produce, as simple as recording one's voice, videocasts are more challenging because it does not only involve audio but also video. Generally, there are two kinds of videocasts; a. Video Lecture and b. Video Slideshow. A video lecture is a video of a teacher who teaches a subject in a classroom setting. The teacher may do his teaching with a whiteboard or flipchart or he delivers his lecture. For this purpose, the teacher only needs a tripod and a video recording device, such as, video camera, DSLR camera, tablet, or a smartphone. In its implementation, the teacher places a video camera device, sitting on a tripod, in front of him and it records him doing his teaching. If the teachers want to shoot video using smartphones/tablets, they need to use a specialized rig, such as, JOBY Griptight, Glif, or iOgrapher. To record video, tablets and smartphones need an app to do the job. iOS users can now use the free iMovie or Camera app (Apple) to shoot and edit video, whereas Android users depend on the mercy of phone manufactures. Fortunately, there is a universal app that Android users can use; YouTube Capture from Google (free). To achieve acceptable visual quality, teachers should pay attention to room lighting (Brookes in Becta) and the lens quality of the video camera. After video shooting, teachers can edit the video and distribute it online, upload into internet, or offline, making CD/DVD copies.

Video slideshow is basically a slideshow, created with slideshow softwares, that contains a lesson with narration. This video is simpler to produce because the teacher can produce it just by sitting in front of a computer and he only has to create a slideshow using, for instance, PowerPoint 2014. Upon finishing, the teacher can record the slideshow with his narration and export the end result into a video. To make the slideshow more interesting, teachers should put visuals (photo) into slideshow. It will be even better if the texts/photos in the slideshow are animated with built-in animated effects in PowerPoint. To achieve visual clarity, the slideshow should take widescreen format (16:9 or 1280 x 720), use sans-serif font (Helvetica or Gill Sans), and apply 30 points font (minimum font size). When the slideshow video is done, the teacher can, again, distribute it online (via YouTube) or offline (burning CD/DVD).

One caveat with videocast approach is the effort to produce video with good audio quality. This problem can be overcome by using an additional audio recording device. For DSLR camera, teachers can use lavalier or shotgun mic. As to smartphones, teachers can still use lavalier mic or direct mic (iRig Mic Cast). If using external microphone is absolutely out-of-the-question, teachers still have another solution. Do the recording in an empty room and speak loud at built-in microphone on camera/computer (laptop).

Video Processing

After making videocasts, teachers can choose to distribute videos directly or edit them on computer for better look. Editing job is quite easy because specialized softwares are plentifully available and a few of them are free. One very simple freeware for video editing is MPEG Streamclip from Squared5.com. In mere 3.2 MB, Streamclip can convert any video into any format. This is really useful when teachers want to share their videocasts on multiple platform/gadgets. Additionally, Streamclip can even convert video into audio. Furthermore, this nifty software allows users to tweak a video in terms of resolution, size, quality, and it has watermark feature. The best part of Streamclip is the editing features that enable its users to do dirty editing such as cutting a video/audio file or joining multiple video/audio clips. Streamclip is available for Macintosh and Windows. For a simple need, such as, video conversion, teachers can go with two freewares; Wondershare and Any Video Converter; which work just like Streamclip but they do not have video editing ability.

For a more professional result, teachers can use the installed softwares on their computers to refine the videos that they have produced. On Macintosh, iMovie is the best one to produce good quality video with its rich features of editing, filters, effects, and multiple platforms export. For Windows users, Windows Movie Maker, pre-installed with Windows OS, can edit video and add effects with a fine quality. More than that, teachers can also edit the audio of the video. Teacher can add narration or alter the audio quality to achieve better result. Besides pre-installed softwares, there are also free softwares for video editing but they are mostly available online. YouTube, for example, gives a chance to a video uploader to edit his video online, right inside YouTube site. On the down side, online service requires a teacher to have a good internet connection. If the videocasts are created on a smartphone, teachers can edit it *in situ* using the available app. On iPhone, there is iMovie for iOS which works like its sibling on desktop, in a simple form. As to Android, free video editing app depends on phone's manufacturer but Android users can use free app, e.g., YouTube Capture. The edited video can then be uploaded straight into YT from smartphone.

Video/Audio Ripping

There might be a time when teachers need make a copy of audio or video materials, taken from a CD or DVD, for classroom usage and they want to do it with less hassle. For this need, there are four useful applications that can help teachers.

iTunes (apple.com/itunes) is a perfect tool to rip audio files from a CD into computer HD (MP3/AAC format). Besides copying all audio files in a CD, teachers can copy only specific files in a CD by ticking particular boxes. In addition, iTunes can compile selected audio files and burn them into CD (AIFF) or data disc (MP3). Audacity can also do copy audio files into computer but it is complicated in terms of procedure but it is powerful for editing audio files, such as, converting audio files into various codec (MP3, AAC, WMA, AIFF), cutting audio files, and tweaking the quality of audio files.

As to video files from DVDs, teachers can make copies in a universal format which can be played in many multimedia gadgets. Since the video file of a DVD (VOB) takes a large space, there is a need to reduce its size and change it in a universal format (MP4). To do that, teachers can use Handbrake (handbrake.fr), which is a free app and available in multiple platforms (Windows, Mac, Linux). With Handbrake, users can convert video file from VOB into MP4/mkv, which is smaller in size and still retain original quality. More than that, Handbrake can export VOB into MP4 (in different screen size resolutions) for various gadgets (iPod to tablet). With this ability, teachers are able to distribute video files to his students who use different gadgets from teachers'. Beyond distribution, the MP4 files enable teachers to edit videos for a specific needs using a video editing software.

Simple Photo Modification

Microsoft Paint and Paint.NET are already famous for free simple photo manipulation but Skitch (evernote.com/skitch) is absolutely useful for an even simpler photo editing task. After years of being a Mac exclusive app, Skitch is recently available for Windows and mobile gadgets (Android and iOS) after its acquisition by Evernote.

Skitch can be described as an application for PDF/photo annotation. Besides that, (for desktop version) Skitch can be used as screen capture with annotation feature, which is really useful if one wants to get an undownloadable photo from a website. The picture, and its annotation, can be exported into JPEG/PDF/PNG (desktop version) for further use. In case of mobile app, Skitch can annotate photo/PDF but it can only export the file into JPEG. To get PDF export feature, user has to make a purchase to Evernote.

Another useful application that can help teacher to develop learning material is an application that can turn a smartphone camera into a scanner. Every once in a while, a teacher might come into a situation when he/she needs to make a copy of a document but a scanner is nowhere to be found. Fortunately, a smartphone camera, and a small application, can act as a scanner and turn a photo into a PDF/JPEG file. CamScanner (Android and iOS) is a tiny application that utilize the camera of a smartphone to capture the image of a document (paper, poster, receipt, brochure, etc) and process the image into a PDF/JPEG file. After it has been processed, users may upload the scanned file into cloud or transfer it into computer (via Bluetooth). Next, the scanned file can be used as to develop a learning material according to the teacher's wish.

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